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RADNEXT Transnational Access Summary Report

Project title	<i>RadFix Space: Software/Hardware Mitigation Assessment of Nvidia Jetson Orin GPUs for space application</i>
Project TA identifier	TA10-343
General application	Space
Type of test	SEE
Group leader, Institute	<i>Ivan Rodriguez-Ferrandez, Barcelona Supercomputer Center</i>
Co-authors, Institutes	<i>Leonidas Kosmidis, Barcelona Supercomputer Center. Eric Rufart, Barcelona Supercomputer Center</i>
Date(s) of the experiment	<i>September 27th, September 28th, September 29th</i>
Facility	GRAND ACCELERATEUR NATIONAL D'IONS LOURDS (GANIL)
Amount of access granted (unit of access: 1h)	24

Objectives of the experiments

In this project we aim to test single events effects on the latest Nvidia Jetson Orin family of boards manufactured in 7 nm process by TSMC. These systems are very complex devices that feature a multicore CPU paired with powerful GPU and AI accelerators. This test is one of multiple radiation tests required to complete my on-going ESA co-funded PhD activity "Mixed SW/HW Fault-Tolerance Techniques for Complex System-on-Chip" in which we aim to develop software and hardware solutions targeting automotive grade systems to be used in space missions. Based on results on the previous generation of Jetson devices, Jetson Xavier, we identified where the main cause of SEFIs are generated (tags structures of caches) and how the system itself corrects most of the SEU generated under proton irradiation. In the new generation of devices, Jetson Orin, preliminary reports indicate that the main issue generating SEFIs has been solved. Based on that we propose to test this new generation of devices to verify that, and if the SEFI are reduced, try to identify SEE happening on the GPU that were previously unable to test due to the high sensitivity of errors on the main CPU.

The selection of the GANIL beam was due to the need of an ion source that works on air, in order to allow proper cooling of the device, as well a high penetration of the ion to allow full penetration on the device.

<https://radnext.web.cern.ch/>

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Experiment test report

Test Preparation

In the scope of this experiment, we tested two NVIDIA Jetson platforms, the NVIDIA Xavier NX and the NVIDIA Orin NX 16GB. With the following serial numbers:

- 1424423004944
- 1420923003683

The NVIDIA Xavier NX is built on the 12 nm TSMC FinFet technology, while the NVIDIA Orin NX is presumably on the 8 nm Samsung FinFet.

For our test in GANIL we were allocated the 47 MeV/u Krypton source.

As highlighted by the Bragg curve, silicon depth is a critical parameter for determining the final LET values during testing. For the Krypton beam at this energy, the Bragg peak for silicon occurs at a depth of approximately 800 µm. Consequently, the initial step was to prepare the silicon die on the DUT, a process commonly referred to as "device opening".

Given that the first test focused on the SoC, and the silicon in this case is directly exposed due to the flip-chip design, only thinning of the silicon was required to prepare the sample.

With the assistance of the European Space Agency (ESA) Materials Laboratory, the silicon on the devices was thinned to a depth of 200 µm, reaching the first metallisation layer. This ensures that up to 200 µm of silicon remains between the exposed surface and the metallization, with the transistors located within this range. The silicon thinning was validated using an infrared laser measurement system. An example of the output from this measurement process is displayed in following figure.

As observed in the Figure, the central region of the silicon has less material compared to the corners. During the thinning process, it was discovered that the silicon is slightly bent, likely due to the large size of the die and the constraints imposed by the BGA package that supports the SoC. This bending effect was consistent across all the DUTs. This phenomenon is further illustrated in the 3D measurement shown in the next figure.

Figure 4-26: Silicon 3D Thickness on one DUT showcasing the bend silicon

All of the devices that were thinned down the highest thickness of 214 μm, with only 2 samples above the 200 μm as shown in following table.

DUT Code	Device	Lowest Thickness (μm)	Highest Thickness (μm)
NX4	Xavier NX	153	204
OR4	Orin NX	146	214

Using the thickness of the devices we calculate the target LET for our test. The test plan included four different LET values: three for the Single Event Effect (SEE) testing phase and one additional LET for the Single Event Latch-up (SEL) testing phase. The specific LET values and their corresponding parameters for the GANIL facility are summarized in the table below.

LET Code	LET at Surface (MeV/(mg/cm ²))	LET at Sensitive (200 μm)	Aluminium Attenuator Thickness (μm)	Air Gap (mm)
LET 1	13.48	15.23	0	110
LET 2	19.49	30.65	400	100
LET 3	21.08	35.5	450	100
LET 4	23.55	40.89	500	115

Test procedure

For this test we used the carrier board Happy Frog (HF) that has been developed for this test in order to not having anything sensitive close to the irradiation area. Also, to focus the Heavy Ion beam to only the areas of interest, a 2 mm aluminium front shield was used. Using 2 mm aluminium ensures that no krypton ions can go to the non-exposed areas.

Because during the SEE test we want to use the GPU we need to provide cooling for the main SoC, we used a blower type fan in order to force air between the front shield and the DUT in order to maintain the maximum temperature bellow 80°C. Beyond this threshold the device starts to reduce the clock frequency in order to avoid overheating. This set up can be observed in the figure below.

For the SEE test, one Xavier NX and one Orin NX, codes *NX4* and *OR4* were used.

SEE Testing

For the SEE testing, we began the experiments with the NVIDIA Xavier board. The device was exposed to three different LET values, during which approximately 100 SEEs were accumulated for each LET. The following Table presents the fluence for each LET and the total number of SEEs recorded.

LET	Fluence	SEE Events	Cross-section
LET 1	2.89×10^5	160	5.54×10^{-4}
LET 2	5.47×10^4	64	1.17×10^{-3}
LET 4	1.59×10^5	105	6.59×10^{-4}

As can be observed, there is a reduction in the cross-section at an LET of 40.89 compared to 30.65. This suggests that we have surpassed the Bragg peak of this ion in silicon, indicating that the measured LET value of 40.89 is incorrect. This conclusion becomes even clearer when the data is visualised in a chart.

Moving to the other DUT, the NVIDIA Orin, we observed behaviour like that of the previous device, with SEEs comparable to those of the NVIDIA Xavier. However, in this case, the number of events was dominated by SEUs, which were corrected by the underlying system.

Due to time constraints, we were able to test only LET 1 and LET 4. The results of this test are presented in the following table.

LET	Fluence	SEE Events	Cross-section
LET 1	3.89×10^5	288	7.41×10^{-4}
LET 4	6.60×10^4	115	1.74×10^{-3}

Similar to the previous test, the exact value of LET 4 is uncertain, but it likely lies somewhere between LET 1 and LET 2. As observed, the cross-section for the NVIDIA Orin is worse than that of the Xavier. However, in the case of the Orin, approximately 80% of the events are SEUs that are corrected by the underlying hardware.

SEL Testing

For the SEL test, we focused our efforts on testing the main SoC. This test involved using all four LETs on the Xavier and the first two LETs on the Orin device. The discrepancy in the number of LETs tested was due to facility issues that led to the early termination of the radiation campaign.

During the initial test with LET 1 on the Xavier, no SEL-related effects were observed, even at a fluence of 1.00×10^7 . However, a different outcome was observed for LETs 2, 3, and 4. During these tests, current peaks exceeding the configured power consumption of the device were recorded. These can be observed on the SEL Cross-section table.

LET	Fluence	SEL Events	Cross-section
LET 1	1.00×10^7	0	1.00×10^{-7}
LET 2	1.00×10^7	25	2.50×10^{-6}
LET 3	1.00×10^7	29	2.90×10^{-6}
LET 4	1.00×10^7	36	3.60×10^{-6}

After the final LET test, the NVIDIA Xavier manages to boot without any issues.

For the Orin, similar to the Xavier, no SEL events were observed at LET 1 and in contrast to Xavier also no SEL events were detected at LET 2. However, in the case of LET 2, we only reached approximately 60% of the intended fluence (6.5×10^6) due to facility issues. Despite this, no SEL events were observed, and the device successfully booted after the test.

LET	Fluence	SEL Events	Cross-section
LET 1	1.00×10^7	0	1.00×10^{-7}
LET 2	6.50×10^6	0	1.54×10^{-7}

Test conclusions

In conclusion, the tests reveal that these devices are highly susceptible to heavy ion irradiation, necessitating the use of the lowest flux available at the facility for these tests. Additionally, we observed differences on the SEE cross-section between generations of the device.

Regarding the SEL events, while SEL events were observed on the devices, these would likely be masked in a real scenario due to the device's sensitivity to functional interrupts.

In the case of the Orin, no SEL events were observed during the two LETs tested.

Outcome of the experiments

Please indicate what the experiment is likely to lead to by putting an 'X' next to one or more of the possible outcomes below.

Journal publication	X
Data for Thesis	X
Follow-up experiment at same facility	
Follow-up experiment at another facility	
Other	

As a RADNEXT user, we encourage you to submit the scientific results of your experiments to journals as well as to the NSREC and RADECS data workshops. Please remember to include the RADNEXT acknowledgment into your publications!

RADNEXT acknowledgment:

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